

New data on the Palaearctic Xantholinini.
13. Systematic position of *Xantholinus laevisissimus* Reitter, 1898
(Coleoptera: Staphylinidae)
276th contribution to the knowledge of the Staphylinidae

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Abstract. *Hypnogyra angularis* (Ganglbauer, 1895) = *Xantholinus laevisissimus* Reitter, 1898, syn. n. is established with a short history of the cited species. First records of *Hypnogyra angularis* (Ganglbauer, 1895) for Crimea and *H. hoffmanni* (Bernhauer, 1928) for South Korea are given.

Riassunto. Nuovi dati sugli Xantholinini paleartici. 13. Posizione sistematica di *Xantholinus laevisissimus* Reitter, 1898 (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae). 276° contributo alla conoscenza degli Staphylinidae. L'autore propone la seguente sinonimia: *Hypnogyra angularis* (Ganglbauer, 1895) = *Xantholinus laevisissimus* Reitter, 1898, syn. n. Vengono riportate le prime segnalazioni di *Hypnogyra angularis* (Ganglbauer, 1895) per la Crimea e di *H. hoffmanni* (Bernhauer, 1928) per la Corea del Sud.

Key words. Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Xantholinini, *Hypnogyra*, new synonymy, new record, Crimea, South Korea.

Xantholinus laevisissimus Reitter, 1898 was described from the Talish territory, now on the border Azerbaijan-Iran, in front of the southern shores of the Caspian Sea. Reitter (l. c.) compared this species with *Xantholinus fasciatus* Hochhuth, 1849 that is a very different taxon previously referred to the genus *Calontholinus* Reitter, 1908, and recently synonymized with the genus *Nudobius* Thomson, 1860 (BORDONI, 2010).

Xantholinus laevisissimus in the past was attributed to the genus *Phalacrolinus* Coiffait, 1972 (COIFFAIT, 1972) (now syn. of *Hypnogyra* Casey, 1906). The taxa of this last genus have been reported for a long time to the genus *Megalinus* Mulsant & Rey, 1877 (COIFFAIT, 1956; SMETANA, 1958; LOHSE, 1964; HORIZON, 1965), so even *X. laevisissimus*, considered related to the most common species of *Phalacrolinus glaber* Gravenhorst, 1802 (subsequently replaced by *H. angularis* Ganglbauer, 1895 because preoccupied name: see TOTTENHAM (1939) and HERMAN (2001)), was attributed to *Megalinus* (BORDONI, 1975). Still now the species of Reitter is placed in *Megalinus* (HERMAN, 2001; SMETANA, 2004).

The study of several specimens of *H. angularis* from Europe (Poland, Germany, Hungary, Bulgaria, Croatia, Italy, Crimea), compared with the description and figure proposed for *X. laevisissimus* in the cited contribution of BORDONI (1975), demonstrates that *H. angularis* and *X. laevisissimus* are the same species, so I propose the following synonymy:

Hypnogyra angularis (Ganglbauer, 1895) = *Xantholinus laevisissimus* Reitter, 1898, **syn. n.**

The species shows some variability both in external characters (size of the body, shape of head, punctuation of pronotum) and in the structure of inner sac of the aedeagus (more or less dense scales on the surface and variable number of the dark spines, from 5 to 7), within populations originating from the same region (for example Crimea). The different disposition of the spines depends on the different arrangement of the inner sac wrapped on itself.

Since the species is new for the Crimean region, I list the new records (all in my private collection): Crimea (Tauria), Simferopoli, W. Pliginsky XI.1912, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; Crimea, Yaltinsky, Taushan-Bazar (?), W. Pliginsky XII.1912, 1 ♂.

Distribution. The species is known from Europe, Turkey, Crimea, Azerbaijan, Iran. In my opinion the numerous citations of Fauvel (cf. HERMAN, 2001) concerning Algeria and Tunisia, must be confirmed.

Bionomics. The species seems to be linked to the cavities and barks of plant (cf. for example WHITEHEAD, 2005: in wood of *Fraxinus excelsior* L. in UK); a rich lot of specimens of a cork in Pomezia (Italy, Lazio, Roma), confirms this thesis. Also cited with ants (e.g. HORION, 1965).

Remarks. The systematic position of *Xantholinus baicalensis* Fauvel, 1875, described from Lake Baikal on the basis of a female (BORDONI, 1975) and related to *Hypnogyra* (Coiffait, 1972, sub *Phalacrolinus*), can be defined only after the study of a male.

In a previous contribution (BORDONI, 2003) for mistake I have referred to *H. tubulus* (Sharp, 1889) four specimens from South Korea (Chungbuk prov., Mt Minjusjisan, Y. C. Cho leg. 20.VIII.1997) (Natural History Museum, Daejon and coll. Bordoni, Firenze, Italy). These specimens must be referred to *H. hoffmanni* (Bernhauer, 1928), known taxon from NE China (BORDONI, 2000). It is very probable that also the specimens related to *H. tubulus* by YUH *et al.* (1985), belong to *H. hoffmanni*. This last species is consequently a new record for South Korea.

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